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Editor-in-Chief: Dr. Theo Gavrielides

ISSN: 2056-2969 | www.rj4allpublications.com/yvj | yvj@rj4allpublications.com

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- Provide a platform for the intellectual exchange of ideas around the globe with the aim of influencing policies and practices
- Actively encourage and aide those young people whose voice is rarely heard by policy makers and academia to be published

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The Journal publishes scholarly papers of the highest standard including: research papers, case studies, book reviews conference papers and proceedings. It has an international and multidisciplinary scope and is particularly interested in work that impacts on social policy and the law.

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